

Research: Insights and Experiences of an ERAU Student

My name is Eugene Pik. This year (2024), I completed the M.S. program in Aviation and Aerospace Sustainability with a specialization in Aviation Cybersecurity at Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University (ERAU). Over the course of two years, I engaged in research activities, which sparked a profound interest and excitement in me.

Recently, two of my peer-reviewed articles were published, and my friends and schoolmates asked me to share my experiences.

Following are my thoughts and experiences, shared in no particular order:

1. Securing a research mentor is invaluable. ERAU provides a research mentoring program called COMPASS <https://worldwide.erau.edu/colleges/arts-sciences/compass>. Choose "Individual Mentorship". By completing the form, you will be assigned a mentor. I had the opportunity to work with Dr. Emily Faulconer, who is brilliant! A mentor can guide you through the processes of publishing, writing, and selecting an appropriate journal, among other tasks.
2. ERAU students, take advantage of the Virtual Communication Lab, VECTOR <https://worldwide.erau.edu/colleges/arts-sciences/vector>. Early on, I scheduled one-on-one meetings with advisers to review my papers at least ten times and received incredible help. This often involved reading sentences aloud, leading to those enlightening '*Gotcha, I see what to fix!*' moments in your own writing.
3. The source data for your research is paramount. My recently published article provided a historical perspective based on secondary sources. Initially rejected as a "research article", it found a home in a journal that welcomes "reviews".
4. Journal rejections are part of the process. A quick rejection (2-4 weeks) is preferable to a prolonged one (6-8 months) as it saves time. Editors typically provide feedback on why an article was rejected, which can be invaluable for making improvements. However, there is no guarantee that addressing these points will lead to acceptance. I found myself in that situation; even after revising my paper according to two pages of comments, it was still rejected by the same editor.
5. Never let rejection discourage you. Persist, revise your paper, and submit it to another journal.
6. Understand the differences between 'open', 'subscription-only', and 'hybrid' journals. Open access entails immediate public visibility post-publication at a cost paid by the author. Subscription-only journals do not charge authors but limit visibility to subscribers. Hybrid journals offer a choice between the two. ERAU hosts completely open and free for authors and readers journals: <https://commons.erau.edu/journals/>. One of my articles I published in an open access journal that does not charge a publication fee (APC): <http://doi.org/10.38008/jats.v13i2.201>
7. Publication timing varies by journal, often advertised as 'time to publication'. My experience falls into the medium scale, though some journals are significantly slower.
8. Never underestimate your abilities. Writing a high-quality article comes with practice and experience. I have encountered extremely talented individuals doubting their work's worthiness for publication. It is crucial to believe in yourself, have a certain level of "chutzpah". Though, still have an attention to detail and listen to your research mentor, even if their comments mean a lot of work/updates/improvements for your paper.
9. Pay attention to journals' specific formatting requirements (font type, size, headings, shoulders, references and citations style etc).
10. Conferences can offer a more accessible publication route. Identify a relevant conference, submit an abstract or paper proposal, and await approval. Upon acceptance, complete your paper for presentation. Some conferences offer a separate track for students, sometimes even including prizes for the best paper competition.
11. ERAU-hosted conferences provide a platform for showcasing research, open to both undergraduate and master's students. Example: ERAU Discovery Day.

12. Stay organized by tracking your submissions and following up with journals regarding the status of your papers. Below is a screenshot of my research activities, a simple Excel file helping to maintain oversight of my work.

#	Name	Type	Initial Status	Notes	Current Status	Full name	URL 1
1	ICAO student competition 2023	Competition	Submitted	Submitted Oct 29 2023, waiting for judges by Q1 2024	Jan 2024 - didn't make to the finals	General Aviation Aircraft as a Meteorological Sensor	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo
2	NASA student competition 2024	Competition	Submitted Feb 27, 2024	Presentation submitted on Feb 27 2024 Video: https://youtu.be/b1GkIVu_zwM	Didn't make to the final	Enhancing Hurricane Forecasting and Alerts through AI-Driven Analysis of General Aviation Data	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo
3	GPS Anomalied, ADS-B, NOTAM AIAA AVIATION Forum, LasVegas	Paper	Approved for presentation	Analyzing geospatial data, billions of records. Received access to ADS-B Trino DB. Received 2022-2023 NOTAMs from FAA. Presentation scheduled for Aug 2, 2024. Proposal submitted Dec 12, 2023.	Abstract accepted. Final submission - June 24 2024	Detecting GPS Anomalies in Aviation Using ADS-B: Correlating Coordinate Gaps and GPS Deviations with NOTAM Warnings	https://www.aiaa.org/events-le
4	eVTOL development ICAO student competition paper	Competition proposal	Sent Nov 29, 2023	abstract sent on Nov 29 Possible questionnaire based. IRB is not required. Paper submission deadline - 15 May 2024	Abstract is not approved	eVTOL Development - High Hopes and Hard Realities in Business and Regulation	https://www.icao.int/Meetings
5	Drones, international statistics - ERAU research	Paper		APAC CAAs - emails sent, responses recorded	Receiving responses, following up with CAAs	Game of Drones, international drone statistics	
6	Drone Propellers AIAA AVIATION Forum, LasVegas	Paper		"ma_web" spreadsheet by Dec 6 2023 - done	Working on the DB of propellers from multiple manufacturers	Empirical Propeller Mass Sizing for Small-Scale Aircraft	
7	AI and Security in Airports	Paper	Submitted Nov 28, 2023	Apr 8, 2024 - published Mar 6, 2024 - accepted for publication. Nov 28, 2023 submitted Journal of Transportation Security (JTS) JAAER - Submitted Jul 10, withdrawn Nov 24, 2023	Apr 8, 2024 - published	Airport Security - The Impact of AI on Safety, Efficiency, and the Passenger Experience	https://doi.org/10.1007/s12198
8	Women in Aviation	Paper	Submitted May 4, 2023	Journal of Air Transport Studies (JATS) - submitted Jan 18, 2024 JATM - submitted May 04, rejected Dec 26, 2023 Jun 7, 2024 - published		Gender Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion in the North American Aviation and Aerospace Industry	https://jats.aviationsociety.org/jr
9	Pilot Shortage	Paper	Submitted Apr 28, 2023	Apr 18, 2024 - accepted for publication JATS Journal of Air Transport Studies - submitted Dec 7 2023 ETRR - submitted Dec 1, rejected Dec 6, 2023 IAAAA - submitted Nov 6 - rejected Nov 25, 2023 (review article) IAAAA - submitted Oct 31 - rejected Nov 5, 2023 (not a research article) JAAER - Submitted Jun 26 - withdrawn Oct 31, 2023 (no response from editor) JATM - Submitted May 31, rejected Jun 26, 2023 JATM - Submitted Apr 26 2023, rejected Apr 28, 2023	Jun 7, 2024 - published	The Pilot Shortage - Implications, Repercussions, and Tried Solutions	https://jats.aviationsociety.org/jr
10	Poster presentation for ERAU Discovery Days 2024	Poster	Submitted Feb 06, 2024	Poster submitted on Feb 06. Submission due date Apr 2nd. Forum Apr 10	May 13, 2024 - Posted on ERAU and Zenodo. Apr 10, 2024 - Presented at Discovery Day 2024	GPT-4 Assisted Categorization and Visualization of NTSB UAV Accident Reports	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo
11	FAA drone stats 2016-2022	spreadsheet	uploaded to Zenodo			Commercial and Recreational Active UAV Fleet in the U.S. 2016-2022	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo
12	Python scripts to categorize NTSB reports using GPT-4	software	uploaded to Zenodo			GPT-4 Assisted Categorization and Visualization of NTSB UAV Accident Reports - Python scripts	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo
13	Utilizing GPT-4 for NTSB UAV Accident Analysis and Categorization	Paper	Submitted	Journal of Safety Research - submitted Jun 6, 2024 Accident Analysis and Prevention - submitted May 22, rejected Jun 6, 2024 (without explanation)	Peer review in progress Jun 10, 2024 - submission accepted, sent to 2 peer reviewers	Utilizing GPT-4 for NTSB UAV Accident Analysis and Categorization	https://track.authorhub.elsevier.ae2f843c717d

13. Use a software to organize references. There are many options, I use Zotero and love it!

14. Zenodo.org (supported and maintained by CERN and OpenAIRE) can be used to store datasets or any intermediate results that may not be significant enough for journal publication but are still important for research and potentially useful to other researchers. It assigns a unique DOI number to your dataset or uploaded materials for easy citation and reference. An example: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11411991>. Sharing your dataset also enhances the credibility of your paper.

15. Create a profile at ORCID. It will assist in logging in or creating accounts at many journals and will keep your researcher identity distinct from other researchers. Example: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6296-919X>.

16. Register on ResearchGate to showcase your achievements and follow others. My profile: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Eugene-Pik-3>.